

Overlooked insects in neglected ecosystem: new records of Phoridae for Slovakia discovered in rural environment

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Abstract: An understudied ecosystem such as a rural area can hold many surprises. In this paper we report the results of a collection at a rural site in eastern Slovakia using a single Malaise trap over a five-month period. From May to September 2023, 70 species of the Diptera family Phoridae were found there, 19 of which represent new species for the Slovak fauna (one sp. of the genus *Aenigmatias* and 18 spp. of the genus *Megaselia*). The species richness of the Phoridae fauna in Slovakia has thus increased by almost 9% to 229 species. It is very likely that more intensive research will yield many more interesting records and greatly increase our knowledge of Slovakia's biodiversity.

Keywords: faunistic, new records, Phoridae, scuttle flies, Slovakia

Introduction

Urban and rural areas are not usually considered to be biodiversity-rich environments. These highly degraded remnants of native habitats, together with highly altered areas occupied by non-native species, are often neglected by researchers, leaving the biodiversity of most towns and villages unstudied or understudied (Hartop et al., 2015). The same applies to the study of Diptera biodiversity (e.g. Hartop et al., 2015).

Inadequate knowledge of the fauna of regions and gaps in information on the occurrence of species may limit the achievement of international biodiversity goals (Girardello et al., 2018; Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2011 and references therein). Comprehensive biological databases based on relevant data are a primary tool in ecological and biogeographical research, as good quality distribution data are required for the development of reliable designs and conservation strategies (Prendergast et al., 1993; Soberón & Peterson,

2004; Guralnick et al., 2007; Hortal et al., 2007). Even though it is challenging (Fattorini, 2013), any faunal information on a little-known group, and especially from an understudied region and ecosystem, is very important. What Hartop et al. (2015) write about urban ecosystems in their excellently titled article 'Opportunity in our Ignorance...' also applies to the rural habitats of scuttle flies, as documented in several papers (Durska, 1981; Prescher & Weber, 1996; Disney, 2001; Langourov, 2004; Hartop et al., 2015; Brown & Hartop, 2017; Grundmann & Kappert, 2023).

Flies of the family Phoridae (Diptera), also known as scuttle flies, are small to medium-sized (0.5–6 mm), often somewhat curved and more or less robust, with characteristic wing venation (Disney, 1983). Adults are conspicuous for their rapid and somewhat abrupt movements (Disney, 1983). Most adults feed on nectar, honeydew and sap oozing from fresh carrion and faeces; some feed on the body juices of live beetle larvae and pupae.

Fig. 1. Malaise trap set on PM's private land.

Phorid flies belong to the lower family Cyclorhapha, a superfamily of Platypezoidea with about 35 genera and more than 700 species in Europe (Oosterbroek, 2006). Recently, 210 species are known from Slovakia (Mocek, 1997, 2009; Grundmann et al., 2023).

Material and methods

Locality data

Slovakia, Prešov District, Lažany Village. Malaise trap (Townes' type) (Fig. 1), 49°02'13.7"N 21°05'45.6"E, leg P. Manko. The trap was placed in a shaded area about 3 m from a small forest stream at the edge of the forest (mainly oak (*Quercus*), hornbeam (*Carpinus*), lime (*Tilia*), with hazel (*Corylus*), birch (*Betula*), poplar (*Populus*), elder (*Sambucus*) and willow (*Salix*) on the edges with a lot of dead wood and standing dry trees and diverse other microhabitats – leaf litter and decomposing leaves, bare soil and stands of moss and herbaceous vegetation) in the immediate vicinity of a mowed lawn (backyard), an orchard, and a compost heap. Considering that the paper deals with the family Phoridae, it is probably

worth mentioning that the trap was located near the local cemetery, the nearest graves being less than 50 m away.

Sampling

Phorid flies were sampled together with other insects using a Malaise trap (see locality data) exposed for one week (7-day period) in each month from May to September 2023 (May (12–16.5.2023), June (16–23.6.2023), July (20–29.7.2023), August (19–23.8.2023), September (19–25.9.2023)). The material collected in ethanol was transported to the laboratory. Collected flies were sorted to family level, fixed in 75% alcohol and identified by group specialists. Phorid flies belong to the dominant dipteran groups in the collected material. Specimens were identified to species level by B. Grundmann using keys (Schmitz, 1943, 1951; Disney, 1983, 1989, 1994, 1999). BG also kept the collection of scuttle flies.

Data on larval biology and feeding ecology were drawn from the following publications: Donisthorpe (1927), Picard (1930), Örösi-Pal (1938), Schmitz (1941, 1943, 1949), Schmutterer (1952), Decou-Burghelle (1961), Lundt (1964), Spradbery (1973),

Disney (1976, 1977, 1991, 1994), Hackman (1963), Yarkulov (1972), Hackman & Meinander (1979), Yakovlev (1986), Köhnhorn (1987), Gemesi & Disney, (1991), Durska (1996, 2001, 2009, 2013, 2015, 2020), Buck (1997), Werner (1997), Ayre (2002), Coupland & Barker (2004), Durska et al. (2005), Craik (2009), Grundmann & Kappert (2023).

Results

A total of 554 scuttle flies were found in the trap (May – 117 individuals, June – 145, July – 160, August – 63, September – 69) belonging to 70 species (see the Annotated list of recorded species). 19 species are recorded for the first time in Slovakia. 31 species were recorded on the basis of only 1 individual. The most abundant species was *Diplonevra nitidula* (Meigen, 1830) with 113 specimens (20% of all recorded specimens), followed by *Megaselia consetigera* (Schmitz, 1925) with 61 specimens (11%), *Chaetopleurophora erythronota* (Strobl, 1892) with 59 specimens (10%) and *Diplonevra abbreviata* (von Roser, 1840) with 48 specimens (8%). Only 5 species were recorded in all seasons and more than half of the species (39) were recorded in only one sampling period (month).

Annotated list of recorded species

For species records only the months are given, for the exact collection period in which the species was caught see Materials and methods. For species new to the Slovak fauna, we also provide some information on the feeding ecology of their larvae, if known. For more abundant species, where it was possible to display and interpret seasonal activity we also provide information on it along with information on feeding ecology, if known.

Diptera

Phoridae

Aenigmatias lubbocki (Verrall, 1877) (Fig. 2). Material examined: May, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia. Zoophagous (Durska, 2015). All species of the genus *Aenigmatias* are myrmecophilous. They are

Fig. 2. A male and a wingless female of *Aenigmatias lubbocki* in copula (photo by www.spessart-fliegen.de .

parasitic on ant pupae (Donisthorpe, 1927; Schmitz, 1941).

Anevrina thoracica (Meigen, 1804). Material examined: July, 1 ♂; September, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀. Note: The saprophagous species is known to fly in two generations from April to July, hibernation as pupa. It is widely distributed all over Europe (Schmitz, 1941). It has been recorded from mammal's nests (Hackman, 1963) and from corpses of small vertebrates (Disney, 1994).

Anevrina urbana (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: May, 1 ♂. Note: Saprophagous, as the previous species (Hackman, 1963; Disney, 1994).

Borophaga femorata (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: May, 4 ♂♂; June, 2 ♂♂. Note: The life history of this species is still unknown (Craik, 2009).

Borophaga germanica (Schmitz, 1918). Material examined: May, 1 ♀; June, 8 ♀♀. Note: The species was only active at the site in spring and early summer. After the peak in June, it was no longer recorded. Zoophagous, recorded to be a parasitoid of larval Bibionidae (Gemesi & Disney, 1991; Langourov, 2004).

Borophaga incrassata (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: August, 4 ♂♂. Note: This species is also known to be a parasitoid of the larvae of Bibionidae (Morris, 1922). Later Grozdanic (1936) reported it as a parasitoid of honey-bees, but this was a misidentification of *Megaselia rufipes* (Örösi-Pal, 1938).

Chaetopleurophora erythronota (Strobl, 1892). Material examined: June, 16 ♂♂, 1 ♀; July, 20 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀; August, 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; September, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀. Note: The species was active at the site in summer

and autumn, with peak activity in July. Zoophagous (molluscivore). *Chaetopleurophora* larvae develop in dead molluscs (Coupland & Barker, 2004, and many references therein).

Conicera tarsalis Schmitz, 1920. Material examined: May, 1 ♂.

Diplonevra abbreviata (von Roser, 1840). Material examined: June, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀; July, 34 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; August, 8 ♂♂. Note: The species was only active in summer, with a peak in activity in July.

Diplonevra concinna (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: July, 1 ♂. Note: The larvae of this saprophagous species have been found in vasp's nests (Spradbery, 1973).

Diplonevra florescens (Turton, 1801). Material examined: May, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; June, 1 ♂; July, 1 ♀; September, 1 ♂. Note: Necrophagous, developing in all kinds of carrion. Three generations from May to October (Schmitz, 1949).

Diplonevra glabra (Schmitz, 1927). Material examined: May, 7 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀. Note: This species is limited to one generation in April and May after Schmitz (1949). But there may be three generations from April to late August (Disney, 1983).

Diplonevra nitidula (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: May, 5 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; June, 15 ♂♂, 23 ♀♀; July, 26 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀; August, 13 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; September, 15 ♂♂, 1 ♀. Note: The species was active throughout the sampling season, with peak activity in June and July. Has been reared from compost (Werner, 1997). The zoophagous larvae have found to be parasitoids of earthworms (Disney, 1991).

Diplonevra pilosella (Schmitz, 1927). Material examined: June, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀; September, 1 ♀. Note: Species whose larvae are reported to be parasitoids of earthworms (Colyer, 1950; Disney, 1991).

Gymnophora arcuata (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: May, 2 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀; June, 2 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; July, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; August, 2 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; September, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀. Note: The species was active throughout the sampling period from May to September, with a marked decrease in activity in September. Saprophagous, breeding in carrion and other decaying material (Coupland & Barker, 2004, and references therein).

Gymnophora integralis Schmitz, 1920. Material examined: September, 1 ♂.

Metopina braueri (Strobl, 1880). Material examined: May, 1 ♂. Note: Zoophagous (Durska, 2013), the diet of this species remains unknown.

Phora atra (Meigen, 1804). Material examined: May, 5 ♂♂; June, 1 ♂. Note: Saprophagous (Durska et al., 2005). Kühlhorn (1987) reported it from cat dung, thus probably coprophagous as well.

Phora edentata Schmitz, 1920. Material examined: May, 4 ♂♂; June, 1 ♂; July, 2 ♂♂.

Phora holosericea Schmitz, 1920. Material examined: May, 5 ♂♂; June, 2 ♂♂. Note: Zoophagous (Durska, 2013). Reported to be a predator of root aphids (Yarkulov, 1972).

Spiniphora bergenstammi (Mik, 1864). Material examined: May, 1 ♂; June, 2 ♂♂; July, 1 ♂. Note: This and the following species are saprophagous. Development in all kinds of carrion (Disney, 1994).

Spiniphora excisa (Becker, 1901). Material examined: June, 1 ♂.

Triphleba distinguenda (Strobl, 1892). Material examined: May, 2 ♀♀; September, 2 ♀♀. Note: Most abundant species of the genus, it is known to fly in three generations from May to November, hibernation as pupa. It is saprophagous and widely distributed in Europe (Schmitz, 1943).

Triphleba dudai (Schmitz, 1918). Material examined: May, 2 ♂♂; June, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; July, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; August, 1 ♂; September, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀. Note: Saprophagous (Lundt, 1964).

Megaselia abdita Schmitz, 1959. Material examined: June, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia. Saprophagous (necrophagous) (Durska, 1996, 2013, 2020; Disney & Manlove, 2005; Manlove & Disney, 2008) or coprophagous (Disney, 1994). The forensic use is described in Greenberg & Wells (1998).

Megaselia aculeata (Schmitz, 1919). Material examined: August, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia albiclava Schmitz, 1926. Material examined: August, 2 ♂♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia breviterga (Lundbeck, 1920). Material examined: May, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀; June, 3 ♀♀; July, 1 ♀; September, 1 ♂. Note: Saprophagous.

Megaselia campestris (Wood, 1908). Material examined: September, 1 ♂.

Megaselia ciliata (Zetterstedt, 1848). Material examined: July, 1 ♀. Note: Zoophagous, this species is known to attack the eggs of land snails (Disney, 1977; Ayre, 2002).

Megaselia clemonsi Disney, 1984. Material examined: July, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia consetigera (Schmitz, 1925). Material examined: May, 7 ♂♂; June, 10 ♂♂; July, 22 ♂♂, 3

♀♀; August, 7 ♂♂; September, 12 ♂♂. Note: The species was active throughout the sampling season with a peak in activity in July and a further increase in activity in September.

Megaselia diversa (Wood, 1909). Material examined: May, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia elongata (Wood, 1914). Material examined: May, 1 ♂. Note: Zoophagous, reported as a parasitoid of Myriapoda (Picard, 1930; Disney, 1994).

Megaselia emarginata (Wood, 1908). Material examined: May, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀; June, 2 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀; July, 2 ♀♀. Note: The species was active throughout the spring and summer, with a peak in activity in July.

Megaselia errata (Wood, 1912). Material examined: May, 1 ♂; August, 1 ♂.

Megaselia flava (Fallén, 1823). Material examined: July, 2 ♀♀. Note: Mycetophagous (Hackman & Meinander, 1979).

Megaselia flavicans Schmitz, 1935. Material examined: June, 1 ♀; July, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; September, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀. Note: The species was active in June and July, with a peak in activity in September after being absent in the August sample. The flight activity of this species indicates two generations per season at the sampling site. Mycetophagous (Disney, 1994).

Megaselia flavicoxa (Zetterstedt, 1848). Material examined: May, 1 ♂; June, 1 ♂; September, 2 ♂♂. Note: Zoophagous, reported as a parasitoid of Sciariidae (Diptera Nematocera) (Disney, 1976).

Megaselia frontalis (Wood, 1909). Material examined: August, 1 ♂.

Megaselia fusca (Wood, 1909). Material examined: May, 5 ♂♂; June, 1 ♂. Note: Saprophagous (coprophagous) (Hackman, 1963).

Megaselia fuscinervis (Wood, 1908). Material examined: June, 6 ♂♂.

Megaselia hortensis (Wood, 1909). Material examined: July, 1 ♂.

Megaselia infraposita (Wood, 1909). Material examined: September, 1 ♂.

Megaselia latifrons (Wood, 1910). Material examined: July, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia latior Schmitz, 1936. Material examined: August, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia. Mycetophagous (Disney & Evans, 1979).

Megaselia ledhuriensis Brues, 1915. Material examined: June, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia. This is the valid name of the species formerly known as *Megaselia subfuscipes* Schmitz, 1935 (Disney, 2014). Zoosaprophagous (Buck, 1997).

Fig. 3. A male of *Megaselia melanocephala*, one of the largest and most striking species in the genus (photo by www.spessart-fliegen.de). Scale bar: 1 mm.

Megaselia lutea (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: May, 2 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀; June, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀; July, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀; August, 1 ♀; September, 1 ♂. Note: The species was active throughout the sampling period with a peak in May and a decreasing trend in activity during the summer and autumn. Mycetophagous (Disney, 1994).

Megaselia lutescens (Wood, 1910). Material examined: September, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia. Mycetophagous (Disney, 1994).

Megaselia manicata (Wood, 1910). Material examined: July, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia melanocephala (von Roser, 1840) (Fig. 3). Material examined: May, 1 ♀; June, 1 ♀; July, 2 ♂♂; August, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia. This zoophagous species is known to be a predator of spider eggs (Decou-Burghelle, 1961).

Megaselia nigriceps (Loew, 1866). Material examined: July, 1 ♀; September, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀. Note: Zoosaprophagous (Durska, 2013).

Megaselia obscuripennis (Wood, 1909). Material examined: August, 1 ♂. Note: Zoophagous.

Megaselia picta (Lehmann, 1822). Material examined: June, 1 ♂; July, 1 ♂; August, 1 ♀.

Megaselia pleuralis (Wood, 1909). Material examined: May, 3 ♂♂; June, 1 ♂; July, 1 ♂. Note: Saprophagous (Disney, 1994).

Megaselia plurispinulosa (Zetterstedt, 1860). Material examined: July, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Note: Mycetophagous.

Megaselia producta (Schmitz, 1921). Material examined: May, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia protarsalis Schmitz, 1927. Material examined: June, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia pseudogiraudii (Schmitz, 1920). Material examined: May, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; June, 3 ♂♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia rubescens (Wood, 1912). Material examined: May, 1 ♂; July, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia. Mycetophagous (Yakovlev, 1986).

Megaselia rufa (Wood, 1908). Material examined: May, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀. Note: This species is known to be a parasite of Coccoidea (Schmutterer, 1952).

Megaselia ruficornis (Meigen, 1830). Material examined: May, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; June, 1 ♂, 7 ♀♀; July, 1 ♀; August, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Note: The species was active from May to August with a peak in June.

Megaselia scutellaris (Wood, 1909). Material examined: September, 2 ♂♂. Note: Mycetophagous.

Megaselia simulans (Wood, 1912). Material examined: September, 1 ♂.

Megaselia spinata (Wood, 1910). Material examined: June, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; August, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia subpleuralis (Wood, 1909). Material examined: September, 1 ♂.

Megaselia subtumida (Wood, 1909). Material examined: September, 1 ♀.

Megaselia tarsalis (Wood, 1910). Material examined: July, 1 ♂. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Megaselia uliginosa (Wood, 1909). Material examined: September, 1 ♂.

Megaselia variana Schmitz, 1926. Material examined: May, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀. Note: First record for Slovakia.

Discussion

In our rapidly changing world, the fauna of towns and villages remains poorly known (Hartop et al., 2015). Similarly, the lack of financial support for local faunistic research and the shortage of specialists means that these ecosystems are understudied.

In this study we report the results of a single Malaise trap catch. 70 species of the family Phoridae have been recorded from a single trap from March to September 2023 in the eastern part of Slovakia. 19 species are recorded for the fauna of Slovakia for the first time. This increases the number of the known phorid species in the country from 210 to 229.

The 554 fly specimens were identified to species level. They belong to 70 species. This is a relatively high number considering that more comprehensive studies have been carried out. For example, two other studies have identified 99 species from 42,000 individuals (Brown & Hartop, 2017) or 52 species from 6,000 individuals (Durska, 2009). According to the results of the first two publications cited above, only about 40 species would be detected with a similar number of individuals as we collected in this study. On the other hand, there are studies that have also recorded very high numbers of species. As an example, Grundmann & Kappert (2023) have found 71 species belonging to other genera than *Megaselia* (from 24,000 individuals). Although differences in species diversity are certainly largely due to differences in the geographical location of sites, but also to differences in approaches and methodologies, local conditions play a particularly important role. Rural landscapes with different landscape features (habitats, habitat types), which differ in terms of management, the presence of different sources of organic matter and potential larval hosts, are therefore likely to provide very suitable conditions for a large number of ecologically diverse species.

The species composition and representation differs from other works, which is a logical consequence of the different approaches to collecting the material and the local conditions at the study sites. Our findings are similar to the results of Grundmann & Kappert (2023), the most abundant species is *Diplonevra nitidula*. If *Megaselia* species were included in their results, the relative abundance of *Diplonevra nitidula* would be exactly the same as we found: 20%. There is also a difference in the abundance of low abundant species, which in our case accounted for up to more than half of the total number of individuals in May and more than a third in September. It is this trend (many low abundance species in spring, a decline in abundance in summer and a resurgence in autumn) that suggests the very real possibility that if we had set the trap throughout the year we would probably have detected significantly more species, especially low abundant or rare species.

In terms of feeding groups, most of the species detected are still unexplored (35), 13 species belonged to zoophages (parasites, parasitoids), 14 to saprophages (including species referred to as necrophages) and 8 to mycetophages. It is pointless to discuss in detail the temporal changes in the representa-

tion of these groups, as the feeding ecology of more than half of the species is unknown and, moreover, the relative abundance of these species varied from close to 30% to more than 50%. Also, given the “patchy” heterogenous pattern of habitat representation at the material collection site, the figure itself is not comparable to the results of other studies conducted in uniform large-scale habitats (e.g., Durska, 2001, 2013, 2015, 2020).

Looking at the sex ratio, we obtained results confirming the overall dominance of males, but the proportions varied from species to species – mostly males dominated, but in some cases females, and in extreme cases only females appeared in the samples. Several authors have found similar and the others different results, and it is generally accepted that the reason for this is a combination of differences in male and female behaviour (and here we add that it certainly differs between species, as we can see in our results) and collection methods (Disney, 1994; Prescher et al., 2002; Durska et al., 2010; Durska, 2013). However, differences in the use of the same method are also interesting. In contrast to the study by Grundmann and Kappert (2023), we found a large number of females (up to 35% of the total number of individuals).

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